

Electrophoretic mobility shift assays (EMSAs): additional information

Since EMSAs are not performed as frequently as SDS-PAGE, additional information will help understanding the nature of these gels:

1. Unlike SDS-PAGE denaturing gels e.g. Western Blots, non-denaturing gel conditions of EMSAs cause a separation by molecular weight, charge, plus three-dimensional structure. In line, EMSA gels do not include any molecular markers. Bands reflect specific binding of proteins of the nuclear extract (mostly transcription factors) to the radioactive-labeled oligonucleotide of the promoter region investigated. Besides this specific protein-oligonucleotide binding, non-specific binding of nuclear proteins to the radioactive-labeled oligonucleotide occur and can often be detected in the background of lanes as darker areas either below or above the specific binding (band). In addition, an excess unbound oligonucleotide probes is detectable at the bottom of the gel.

IN CONCLUSION: If larger areas of **non-specific binding complexes** are visible in several lanes at a similar region it only indicates that several nuclear proteins interact in a non-specific way with the radioactive-labeled probe in each sample loaded.

2. **Electrophoresis.** Unlike SDS-PAGE gels, EMSAs run at very high voltage, 2 hrs at 4°C, not to overheat and melt the gel! ...'Using **radioisotope-labeled nucleic acids**, the assay is **highly sensitive**, allowing the assays to be performed with ... **nucleic acid concentrations (0.1 nM or less)**...' (NATURE PROTOCOLS, VOL.2 NO.8, 2007) and exposure times are very short (few hours) (also see <https://currentprotocols.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf>).

IN CONCLUSION: The fast running conditions of a 5-6% non-denaturing gel in combination with extremely short exposure times result in a higher likeliness of very similar appearances of bands among lanes compared to e.g. SDS-PAGE denaturing gels.

3. Detection of electrophoretic bands and the **appearance of ,background structures'** in lanes: After the run, the gel is transferred in a wet stage to layers of filter papers. Unlike blotting membranes used for Western Blots, 3M filter papers are more structured and transfer occurs by **manually pressuring** filter papers on the wet gel. CRITICAL STEPS: '... **Residual buffer trapped between the plates can promote vacuum formation** In addition, transfer of **free buffer** to the gel surface **can result in elution of radioactive nucleic acid from the gel** This **'free' radioisotope is a nuisance to autoradiography'** ... the gel is wrapped in a **layer of plastic food wrap**. **The wrapped surface of the gel should be free of air bubbles and wrinkles**, since **these will interfere with autoradiography**... **drying the gel on a paper** for exposure... (NATURE PROTOCOLS, VOL.2 NO.8, 2007). During experimental procedures an appearance of 'free' radioisotopes derive either from buffer chambers or eluted from the gel is always a possibility.

IN CONCLUSION: Background structures/patterns/lines are caused by 'free' radioisotopes having infiltrated wet piles of filter papers or being trapped in wrinkles and air bubbles of the plastic food foil wrapped around the gel/filter paper assembly. 'Free' radioisotopes are dried later on during gel drying and can cause very weak radioactive background signals on the autoradiogram including partial visualization of 3M paper structures.